

D2.4 Overview of the communication service provision and lessons learned

Project Title	Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions
Project Acronym	RDA TIGER
Grant Agreement No	101094406
Instrument	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01
Topic	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-04
Start Date of Project	1 January 2023
Duration of Project	36 months
Project Website	https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

Work Package	WP2 - Communications
Lead Author (Org)	Alex Delipalta (RDA AISBL)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Filomena Minichiello (RDA AISBL), Genevieve Halbert (RDA AISBL), Rosie Allison (RDA AISBL), Curtis Sharma (RDA AISBL)
Due Date	31 December 2025
Date	30 December 2025
Version	1.0
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877228

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Authors	Notes
0.1	1/10/2025	Genevieve Halbert (RDA AISBL), Rosie Allison (RDA AISBL)	Draft ToC, executive summary, sections 2.1, 6
0.2	2/12/2025	Alex Delipalta (RDA AISBL), Filomena Minichielo (RDA AISBL)	Content ready for internal review
0.3	15/12/2025	Athina Papadopoulou (RDA AISBL), Trish Radotic (ARDC)	Internal review completed
1.0	30/12/2025	Alex Delipalta (RDA AISBL), Filomena Minichielo (RDA AISBL), Curtis Sharma (RDA AISBL)	Document finalised for submission

Disclaimer

RDA TIGER has received funding from the European Commission’s HORIZON Coordination and Support programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101094406. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIDV	Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation
CERN	Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire
CNRS	Centre national de la recherche scientifique
CTR	Click-through rate
DCC	Digital Curation Centre
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
GA	Grant Agreement
GORC IM WG	Global Open Research Commons International Model Working Group
HOSI	Hellenic Open Science Initiative
I-ADOPT	Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology
IDCC	International Digital Curation Conference
IDW2025	International Data Week 2025
KB	Knowledge Base
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
maDMPs	Machine-Actionable Data Management Plans
MaLDReth	Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools
MOMSI	Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration

PID	Persistent Identifier
PRO4RS	Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software
RDA	Research Data Alliance
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SSH	Social sciences and humanities
TRSPs	Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a final overview of the RDA TIGER communication service provision and outlines key lessons learned throughout the project's implementation. As the concluding report of Work Package (WP) 2 on Communications, it reflects on the evolution, delivery, and impact of the communications activities and service designed to support the RDA TIGER Working Groups (WGs), amplify project outputs, and engage both internal and external stakeholders across the European Open Science landscape.

The RDA TIGER project was established to support the development of high-impact, internationally aligned outputs by providing a suite of support services and grants to RDA Working Groups, with a particular focus on those contributing to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). WP2 played a central role in this effort by designing and delivering a service communications offering tailored to the lifecycle of each WG, from initial idea dissemination and internal coordination, to output promotion and adoption-focused outreach.

Building on the planning and frameworks established in Deliverables D2.1 Communication Toolkit¹, D2.2 Updated Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation², and D2.3 European Network Engagement Progress³, this final report presents an integrated view of WP2 implementation. It documents how the communications service matured from its pilot phase into a responsive, high-impact component of the RDA TIGER support platform, working closely with the supported WGs across each lifecycle stage. It highlights the collaboration with the facilitation and landscape services as well as the RDA Knowledge Base⁴ (KB) development team, and presents how the service strategically showcased the importance and impact of the project as a whole to the broader research data community.

WP2 activities enabled increased visibility of RDA TIGER WGs across Europe, strengthened engagement with RDA Regions and European infrastructures, and supported the dissemination and adoption of WG outputs through events, webinars, targeted communications, and cross-project synergies.

This deliverable also reports on metrics and analytics to showcase the impact of communication activities, and reflects on key lessons learned. It highlights the importance of embedding communications into WG workflows from the start, and the value of tailoring support to co-chair experience levels and specific requirements.

As RDA TIGER concludes, the communication service leaves behind a portfolio of reusable resources, a strengthened presence for RDA WGs and their Outputs within the European Open Science landscape,

¹ Delipalta, A., & Halbert, G. (2024). RDA TIGER D2.1 Communication Toolkit (version 2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14500639>

² Halbert, G., & Delipalta, A. (2024). RDA TIGER D2.2: Updated Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities (version 2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14386006>

³ Halbert, G., Lehtsalu, L., & Delipalta, A. (2025). RDA TIGER D2.3: Report on the progress of European national network engagement in RDA TIGER WGs. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775225>

⁴ <https://www.kb-rda.org/>

and a set of good practices that can inform both the RDA’s future operations and similar initiatives aiming to connect global standards with European priorities.

Table of contents

Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction	10
2. Overview of the RDA TIGER Communication Service	10
2.1 Evolution of the communication plan over time.....	10
2.2 Service Structure & Delivery Phases.....	11
2.3 Service Requests and Working Group Support.....	12
2.3.1 Communications service request process.....	12
2.3.2 Tailored Support Across WG Lifecycle Phases.....	13
2.3.2.1 Tailored Support for WGs starting out (C1).....	13
2.3.2.2 Tailored Support for main WG period (C2).....	14
2.3.2.3 Tailored Support for WG end period (C3).....	16
2.3.3 Communications support offered to WGs primarily receiving facilitation support.....	17
2.3.4 Communications support offered to groups receiving dedicated communications support.....	18
2.4 Communication Means, Tools & Platforms.....	21
3. Service Implementation Highlights	25
3.1 RDA TIGER Cross fertilisation webinars.....	25
3.2 RDA TIGER supported WG Plenary pre- and post- event campaigns.....	26
3.3 Data for AI: From Readiness to Ethics - a panel discussion showcasing the RDA AIDV WG.....	27
3.4 The RDA Knowledge Base.....	28
4. Performance Monitoring & Impact	29
4.1 KPIs and Target Outcomes: Definition & Tracking.....	29
4.2 Analytics and impact.....	29
4.2.1 Website analytics.....	29
4.2.2 Newsletter analytics.....	32
4.2.3 Social Media analytics.....	33
4.2.4 Webinar analytics.....	35
4.2.5. Reflections on impact of communication activities.....	37
4.3 Working Group Feedback and Satisfaction.....	38
5. Stakeholder engagement overview	39

5.1 Engagement with the RDA Community.....	44
5.2 EOSC ecosystem & Broader European Community.....	46
5.3 Cross-Project Synergies.....	46
6. Communications Materials & Resources.....	48
6.1 Evolved use of Branding.....	48
7. Reflections and lessons learned.....	49
8. Conclusion.....	51
Annex 1. WP2 Key Performance Indicator report.....	53

List of figures and tables

List of tables

Table 1. Summary of evolution in implementation of the service blueprint C1.....	13
Table 2. Summary of evolution in implementation of the service blueprint C2.....	15
Table 3. Summary of evolution in implementation of the service blueprint C3.....	16
Table 4. Examples of WG support requests.....	17
Table 5. Sample social media engagement analysis during IDW2025.....	34
Table 6. Sample of webinar participation in the period October 2025 - December 2025.....	36
Table 7. RDA TIGER stakeholders.....	39

List of figures

Figures 1, 2, & 3. GORC IM WG Communique, first produced by WP2 in 2023. Content updated in October 2025, and translated in French in December 2025.....	19
Figures 4 & 5. White paper produced by WP2 for the National PID Strategies WG as part of the dedicated communication service.....	20
Figure 6. Social media promotion of the RDA TIGER continuously open call for support services.....	21
Figures 7, 8, 9. Left to right: Social media promotion of RDA WG meeting, RDA TIGER-supported WG sessions at RDA Plenaries, supported WG adoption story.....	22
Figures 10 & 11. RDA TIGER exhibition table at RDA Plenary 23 in Costa Rica, November 2024, featuring event collaterals, GORC IM WG printed communiques, RDA Knowledge Base Demo booth.....	23
Figures 12 & 13. Joint exhibition table at EOSC Symposium 2023 showcasing RDA TIGER, WorldFAIR and EOSC Future/RDA Domain Ambassador programme.....	23
Figure 14. RDA TIGER WG Plenary sessions social media campaign at IDW2025.....	26
Figure 15. Live polling results snapshot during ‘DATA for AI’ panel at OSFAIR 2025 featuring the RDA AIDV WG (presentation: Natalie Meyers).....	27
Figure 16. Overview of user engagement on pages on RDA TIGER-related web pages on the RDA website..	

30

Figure 17. RDA TIGER user visits geographical distribution..... 30

Figure 18. RDA TIGER new and returning user analytics for the period 9 October 2024 - 2025.....31

Figure 19. RDA Newsletter analytics, which included RDA TIGER featured updates for the period January 2024 - December 2025.....32

Figures 20 & 21. RDA TIGER LinkedIn posts with the most interactions: 411 clicks and 1,200 impressions and 222 clicks and 1,326 impressions, respectively.....33

Figure 22. Mentimeter presentation at RDA Plenary 24 TIGER-organised adoption session.....45

Figure 23 & 24. Examples of early project social media assets.....48

Figures 25 & 26 Examples of updated project social media assets.....49

1. Introduction

The RDA TIGER Communication Work Package set out to provide bespoke support services to the RDA TIGER Working Groups (WGs), while also ensuring high level service awareness of across the service suite, and supporting day to day project communication and outreach activities. Although WP2 worked closely with all other WPs and RDA Secretariat in support of the global RDA community, Europe was its main focus. It played a key role in the project’s achievements and uptake of the service offering. The impact of the communication activities is evident by the significant uptake of the project services by the RDA community but also the new membership brought on board.

The communication service delivered under this work package provided focused, strategic, continuous and often bespoke support for all communication and dissemination activities across the RDA TIGER project, in alignment with other WPs for each component of the service suite and the project as a whole. Tasks supporting the communication service were: Communication Tools Creation and Update (2.1); Communications and Dissemination Service Provision (2.2); and Connection to National Networks in Europe (2.3).

This report provides an overview of the communication and outreach activities both at WG level for each lifecycle / service stage and at the project and service awareness levels, and assesses their effectiveness based on analytics and metrics. It builds on previous WP2 deliverables reporting against the service definition and blueprint, service provision activities and stakeholder engagement, and also by providing an update and key highlights of exploitation activities outlined previously (D.2.2⁵).

2. Overview of the RDA TIGER Communication Service

2.1 Evolution of the communication plan over time

The RDA TIGER communication plan evolved significantly throughout the project lifecycle, reflecting the maturing needs of the communication service, the diversity of WGs onboarded, and the growing complexity of stakeholder engagement.

In the early stages of the project, WP2 focused primarily on raising awareness of the RDA TIGER service platform itself, and defining the anticipated service structure. The communication strategy in this period centred around brand identity, messaging consistency and service visibility to engage the RDA community and encourage applications from WGs. Communications activities during this “service awareness and pilot” phase (as described in D2.2, section 5.2.1) were broad in scope, targeting the RDA

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14386006>

community as a whole and positioning RDA TIGER within the broader landscape. As the first cohorts of WGs were selected and onboarded, the communications plan was adapted to include bespoke strategies tailored to individual WGs, as outlined in D2.2, section 6.2. This adaptation reflected a shift from general promotion to targeted, co-created communication plans aligned with each WG’s maturity, outputs, target adopters, and thematic focus.

By mid-project, WP2 had fully operationalised this tiered service model, enabling more granular support that accommodated experienced RDA co-chairs, RDA newcomers, and pre-existing WGs joining RDA TIGER mid-lifecycle. In parallel, the communication plan was also adapted in response to insights from national engagement efforts (D2.3), which highlighted the value of regional and thematic networks for output dissemination. As a result, WP2 began integrating cross-promotion via RDA regions, EOSC-related projects, and stakeholder-specific networks more systematically into WG communication plans. This adaptation increased the potential for adoption and helped tailor messaging to national contexts.

Throughout the project, the communications plan remained a living document, responsive to feedback from WG co-chairs, coordination with the facilitation and landscape teams, and evolving stakeholder needs.

In summary, the communication plan progressed from a static, project-wide strategy into a modular, service-oriented communications framework, rooted in user needs and collaborative design. This adaptability proved essential for meeting the diverse requirements of WGs and ensuring that communication efforts remained aligned with the strategic objectives of the RDA TIGER project and the broader EOSC ecosystem.

2.2 Service Structure & Delivery Phases

The RDA TIGER communications service was delivered for the three following sub-categories of RDA WGs:

- RDA TIGER Pilot Demonstrator WGs
- RDA TIGER WGs primarily receiving facilitation support⁶ in response to the continuously open calls for in support⁷
- RDA TIGER WGs that specifically applied to an open call requesting communication support (I-ADOPT)

⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/#TIGERgroups>

⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/open-call-rda-working-group-facilitation-support/>

The type of support provided depended on the specific WG needs and co-chair preferences, the target audience, and the WG lifecycle stage.

WP2 communication effort was provided as follows:

- dedicated communications professionals focused on material creation, publication and production (graphics, posters, drafting of communiqués and white papers), as well as social media and website management, newsletter coordination, event and webinar organisation and RDA Secretariat liaison for alignment with RDA global and overall WG overview;
- facilitators communicating WG requests to dedicated WP2 personnel for implementation, and carrying out direct outreach to potential new members at the instruction of WG co-chairs.

2.3 Service Requests and Working Group Support

D2.2 outlined a process for service delivery which evolved over time. Service leads worked closely together, refining workflows and adapting to feedback and WG needs (see also D6.5⁸). The process adopted by RDA TIGER for communication service provision is described below.

2.3.1 Communications service request process

RDA WGs were invited to submit applications to receive RDA TIGER support throughout the lifetime of the project through the continuously open calls for support. Each WG was requested to complete one application form for all services, elaborating on the types of support needed. The facilitation service, the core of RDA TIGER, was overwhelmingly the most popular support service for the community. Facilitators, as those carrying out the core RDA TIGER activity, were subsequently tasked with being the entry-point to the rest of the RDA TIGER services, informing their assigned WGs about the available in-kind support services, and connecting WG co-chairs with the rest of the service leads.

The requests from WGs primarily receiving facilitation support were communicated to the WP2 personnel by facilitators and WP5 (Facilitation) through a dedicated slack channel and communication schedule spreadsheet, and progress was monitored during dedicated meetings taking place every two weeks. The implemented workflow used a flexible, demand-driven model that prioritised responsiveness, co-creation, and alignment with RDA TIGER's broader facilitation and adoption goals. A service mediated by WP5 was needed, as the facilitators were in attendance at all WG meetings, up to date with all WG development and best placed to understand and communicate WG needs to WP2. Specific, communication-focused meetings between co-chairs and WP2 took place for Pilot WGs and

⁸ O'Connor, R., Grau, N., Saldner, S., Minichiello, F., Lehtsalu, L., Delipalta, A. (2025). RDA TIGER D6.5: Final quality evaluation report on the RDA TIGER WG services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877446>

those WGs receiving dedicated communication support with bespoke needs (Global Open Research Commons International Model (GORC IM) WG⁹, National PID Strategies WG¹⁰, Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology WG (I-ADOPT WG)¹¹).

2.3.2 Tailored Support Across WG Lifecycle Phases

Throughout the RDA TIGER project, the communications team responded to a wide range of service requests from WGs primarily receiving facilitation support. Requests typically fell into several recurring categories: promotional material creation, event support, social media coordination, stakeholder-targeted dissemination, and internal communications tools. WP2 tailored each response based on WG maturity, lifecycle stage and urgency. The core of the service workflow followed the blueprints developed in D2.2: ‘Updated Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities’. This section provides an update on the delivery of the service compared to the initial blueprints developed at project kick-off, and comments on the aspects of the service that evolved.

2.3.2.1 Tailored Support for WGs starting out (C1)

At C1 stage, support started from the application process and was carried out until the WG progressed to stage C2 and the main WG work period. C1 support was underpinned by service awareness and the project level communication and outreach activities. Table 1 below presents an overview of the evolution of the service provision under stage C1. All activities were carried out according to this high level blueprint, and WGs received the planned support through a combination of communication personnel, facilitators and WP6 leads.

Table 1. Summary of evolution in implementation of the service blueprint C1

Service stage	Plan outlined in D2.2	Implementation, variations and comments
C1.1	Communications to applicants carried out by the Communication Service	During the project lifetime activity transferred to WP6 as part of the application submission and review process based on templated communications drafted by WP2

⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/gorc-international-model-wg/activity>

¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/national-pid-strategies-wg/activity>

¹¹

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/interoperable-descriptions-observable-property-terminology-wg-i-adopt-wg/activity>

Service stage	Plan outlined in D2.2	Implementation, variations and comments
C1.2	Communication Service coordinates with facilitator team to plan outreach activities	Activity carried out as planned.
C1.3	Communication Service liaising with WG on specific needs and requirements	Activity mediated by facilitators acting under WP2 and the communication service. The distribution of activities took place as follows: -Internal WG communications were managed by facilitators as the main contact points for WGs. -External communications needs were discussed between WG and facilitators and subsequently communicated to WP2 for implementation.
C1.4	Communication Service drafts dissemination plan	Activity carried out as one consolidated communication plan across supported WGs primarily receiving facilitation support. Dedicated communication plans were developed for WGs receiving dedicated communication support.

Activities carried out under C1 were in line with WG requirements and RDA processes and workflows. These activities focused on publication and promotion of kick-off meetings and Statements of Work on the consortium’s social media channels, mailing lists and the RDA Newsletter, and in particular RDA Europe and the global organisation (e.g., website and newsletter). In addition, there was direct communication and outreach by email to potential new members and co-chairs in consultation with WG co-chairs and facilitators. Extensive examples of WG support for C1 against the relevant KPIs are provided in D6.5¹², and also included in Annex 1 of this report.

2.3.2.2 Tailored Support for main WG period (C2)

Table 2 below presents the service provision workflow that was implemented for stage C2. This support stage lasted until the submission of the WG outputs for community review. As with C1, this type of support was also closely dependent on the overall project awareness and efforts to increase visibility of RDA WGs and their outputs as a whole. This support was available to WGs that applied for RDA TIGER

¹² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877446>

support while already at this lifecycle stage, and those who were created through the project and transferred over from C1. Activities were based on ongoing liaison with the WG co-chairs regarding requirements and priorities depending on each WG’s particular needs and requests.

Table 2. Summary of evolution in implementation of the service blueprint C2

Service stage	Plan outlined in D2.2	Implementation, variations and comments
C2.1	Coordination with the facilitator as the main point of contact for WG to plan stage-specific activities.	Activity carried out as planned.
C2.2	Coordination with the supported WG members and co-chairs about collecting specific requirements.	In line with previous stage workflows, this activity was mediated by facilitators acting under WP2 and the communication service. The distribution of activities took place as follows: -Internal WG communications managed by facilitators as main contact points for WGs. -External communications needs were discussed between WG and facilitators and subsequently communicated to WP2 for implementation.
C2.3	Communication Service creates (for WGs accepted for TIGER support at C2 stage) OR updates the plan generated at C1 (if WG is transferring from the previous support stage)	As with C1, this activity was carried out as one consolidated communication plan across supported WGs primarily receiving facilitation support. New onboarded WG needs were scoped in collaboration with the facilitators and incorporated in the master RDA TIGER supported WG communication plan.

C2 activities focused on material creation, ongoing outreach for new members, promotion of interim deliverables, promotion of contributions to external (non-RDA events), promotion of Plenary sessions, organisation of webinars, promotion of WGs to events, etc (see also D6.5¹³, and Annex 1).

¹³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877446>

2.3.2.3 Tailored Support for WG end period (C3)

The C3 support workflow is presented in table 3 below. Carrying over from C2, support activities centred around close consultation with facilitators and WGs and were tailored to specific WG requirements. As with C2, this included WGs that applied for TIGER support while at this lifecycle stage, as well as WGs created with RDA TIGER having received C1 and C2 support. Support in this stage concluded with final output dissemination after RDA endorsement.

Table 3. Summary of evolution in implementation of the service blueprint C3

Service stage	Plan outlined in D2.2	Implementation, variations and comments
C3.1	Coordination with the facilitator as the main point of contact for WG with regards to making the WGs aware of the available communication support, and initial planning of activities.	Activity carried out as planned.
C3.2	Coordination with the supported WG members and co-chairs about collecting specific requirements.	As with C1 and C2, this activity was mediated by facilitators acting under WP2 and the communication service. The distribution of activities took place as follows: -Internal WG communications were managed by facilitators as main contact points for WGs. -External communications needs were discussed between WG and facilitators and were subsequently communicated to WP2 for implementation.
C3.3	Communication Service creates (for WGs accepted for TIGER support at C3 stage) OR updates the plan generated at C1/C2 (if WG is transferring from the previous support stage)	In line with C1 and C2, activity carried out as one consolidated communication plan across supported WGs primarily receiving facilitation support. New onboarded WG needs were scoped in collaboration with the facilitators and incorporated in the master RDA TIGER supported WG communication plan.

Specific activities as part of C3 communication included: promotion of outputs in community review on RDA Europe’s digital channels enabling broad community interaction and feedback; organisation of webinars; promotion of WGs in third party events. Specific examples are provided in D6.5¹⁴, and Annex 1 of this report.

2.3.3 Communications support offered to WGs primarily receiving facilitation support

Below are selected examples that illustrate the diversity and nature of service requests handled by WP2 for WGs receiving primarily facilitation support.

Table 4. Examples of WG support requests

Working Group	Request Summary	Support Provided
Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration (MOMSI) WG	Promotion of the MOMSI landscape analysis dashboard	Creation of dedicated blog post on the RDA website, corresponding social media promotion, and inclusion in the RDA Europe newsletter
Ethics in Agricultural Data WG	Dissemination of survey designed to help the WG understand current practices and perspectives regarding the ethical treatment of agricultural data	Social media promotion and inclusion in the RDA Global newsletter
The Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model WG	Drafting, designing, printing and distributing two communiques for two distinct target audiences to be used at events	Drafting, designing, printing and distributing two communiques for two distinct target audiences to be used at events (figures 1, 2 & 3)

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877446>

Working Group	Request Summary	Support Provided
National PID Strategies WG	Drafting, designing, printing and distributing a white paper and infographic to be used at events	Drafting, designing, printing and distributing a white paper and infographic to be used at events (figures 4 & 5)
APIs for Machine-Actionable Data Management Plans WG	Logo and branded banner image for use on RDA website group page	Design of bespoke logo and banner (no longer published because of web platform updates)
Alignment of multilingual Vocabularies in SSH WG	Targeted communications to attract new members to the group	Creation of dedicated blog and news posts ^{15 16} , dissemination of short promotional video

2.3.4 Communications support offered to groups receiving dedicated communications support

In addition to reactive, facilitator-mediated communications support provided to WGs across the RDA TIGER portfolio, a smaller number of WGs received dedicated communications support via direct engagement with WP2. This dedicated support involved planning meetings between WP2 and WG co-chairs to define bespoke communication strategies (for example, large-scale outreach campaigns, multichannel dissemination of outputs, or sustained promotional activity around a time-bound event series). In these cases, WP2 led or co-developed a communication plan that could be delivered collaboratively and adapted as needed.

This approach was applied to the **I-ADOPT (Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology) WG**, specifically around design, promotion, and follow-up of their Variable Modelling Workshops in 2025. To support this two-part workshop series, WP2 held a dedicated planning session

¹⁵

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/introducing-the-alignment-of-multilingual-vocabularies-in-the-social-sciences-and-humanities-working-group/>

¹⁶

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/join-the-alignment-of-multilingual-vocabularies-in-the-social-sciences-and-humanities-wg-kick-off-meeting/>

with WG co-chairs to identify communications goals, target audiences and success metrics. Based on this discussion, WP2 provided a comprehensive package of communications services, including:

- Creation of dedicated posts on the RDA website advertising the aims and objectives of the workshop series¹⁷.
- Drafting and scheduling of promotional content across RDA Europe digital channels, including the RDA website, Twitter/X, and LinkedIn¹⁸.
- Coordination with the RDA Secretariat to ensure coverage in the global RDA newsletter.
- Post-event amplification, including promotion of session recordings, summary blog posts, and continued visibility of the I-ADOPT outputs and use cases^{19 20}.

The result was a well-publicised workshop series that strengthened the visibility of I-ADOPT within and beyond the RDA community. The WG reported satisfaction with the communication service and with the results of the workshop series.

One of the first pre-selected WGs that received dedicated communication support was the **Global Open Research Commons International Model WG (GORC IM WG)**.

Figures 1, 2, & 3. GORC IM WG Communiqué, first produced by WP2 in 2023. Content updated in October 2025, and translated in French in December 2025.

¹⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/announcing-the-i-adopt-variable-modeling-challenge/>

¹⁸ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7298237496407085057>

¹⁹ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7304852371245858816>

²⁰ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7310627672135553024>

After a set of initial consultations, WP2 worked with co-chairs on a communication plan and stakeholder analysis. Based on this, the WG requested the preparation of two communiqués intended for two distinct audiences, namely funders²¹ and implementers²². WP2 handled the drafting, designing and printing of these communiqués, for the most part distributed at RDA Plenaries. The documents were prepared in 2023, and updated in 2025. They were also translated into French.

The second pre-selected RDA WG that received dedicated communication support was the **National PID Strategies WG**. As before, consultations took place between WP2 and the co-chairs, and it was agreed that the communication service would prepare a white paper²³ on the topic of PIDs and the role of the WG's output, and an infographic²⁴ based on the WG's output. As both of these WGs were at WG end period (C3), the planned activities aimed to support amplification of outputs and broader dissemination.

Figures 4 & 5. White paper produced by WP2 for the National PID Strategies WG as part of the dedicated communication service

²¹ Delipalta, A. (2023). Global Open Research Commons International Model RDA Working Group: Considerations for Developing Policy with Global Impact. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14341560>

²² Delipalta, A. (2023). Global Open Research Commons International Model Working Group: Adopting and Implementing the Model for your organisation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14341230>

²³ Delipalta, A. (2023). National PID Strategies: What, why, how - and where next?. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14340813>

²⁴ Delipalta, A. (2023). Checklist: Pathways to National PID Strategies. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14340259>

2.4 Communication Means, Tools & Platforms

The various means by which RDA TIGER engaged the RDA community and broader stakeholders is presented below.

RDA website

WP2 employed a wide range of tools to carry out the communication support service. As per the GA, the project did not create a separate web presence, but used the RDA website and RDA AISBL / RDA Global communication channels. The core of the communication activities took place on the RDA website²⁵, in the following ways:

- Dedicated RDA TIGER web space visible from the main landing page²⁶ listing all related activities, events, open calls and project information
- News items, blog posts, event publication²⁷
- Direct posting on WG pages and cross-posting items of interest tailored to each WG²⁸

Social media

A wide range of social media platforms were trialed, including Mastodon²⁹, X³⁰, BlueSky³¹ and LinkedIn³². After an assessment of user response and engagement metrics in 2024, LinkedIn was identified as the most suitable platform, and was used as the primary space for RDA TIGER promotion activities across the project (support stages C1-C3 and project awareness).

Figure 6. Social media promotion of the RDA TIGER continuously open call for support services

²⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

²⁶ Current web platform: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/> For the RDA TIGER pages pre-website migration see: <https://archive.rd-alliance.org/get-involved/calling-rda-community/rda-tiger>

²⁷ https://www.rd-alliance.org/news-stories/?_keyword=tiger&_news_type=blogs%2Cnews

²⁸ Example posts:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/computational-modelling-of-health-data/posts?post=197390>,

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/computational-modelling-of-health-data/posts?post=229468>,

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-reproducibility-checklist-working-group/posts?post=190239>,

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/sample-type-classification-wg/posts?post=188587>

²⁹ https://mastodon.social/@RDA_Association

³⁰ https://x.com/RDA_Europe

³¹ <https://bsky.app/profile/rdaeurope.bsky.social>

³² <https://www.linkedin.com/company/rda-europe>

The RDA AISBL accounts were used for RDA TIGER purposes, amplified by project partners and RDA global social media accounts, also in coordination with RDA Secretariat and through the dedicated RDA global communications liaison.

Research Data Alliance Europe
1,294 followers
2mo • 🌐

Join the 'Alignment of #multilingual #vocabularies in the #SocialSciences and #Humanities' Working Group Meeting on September 30, 08:00 UTC.

This Working Group is developing a set of recommendations for the alignment of multilingual vocabularies and aims to engage those who define vocabularies, or develop tools/workflows that support vocabulary alignment.

Interested in getting involved in this group? Now is your chance! Learn how to join the meeting, here: <https://ow.ly/eyBj50WY3Pu>

Working Group Meeting
Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities Working Group

OPEN TO ALL

30 September | 08:00 UTC

RDA TIGER
EOSC

Liise Lehtsalu and 1 other 1 repost

Research Data Alliance Europe
1,294 followers
2mo • 🌐

We're kicking off day 3 of **International Data Week (IDW)**!

Spot the RDA TIGER-supported WG sessions today:

Breakout 3 (01:30 - 03:00 UTC)

- From ethics to interoperability: how to best collect and manage your drone data, Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data Working Group
- Bridging AI international policy and practice: the AIDV approach, Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation (AIDV) WG

Join us in Brisbane and online!

Research Data Alliance (RDA) CODATA #RDAPlenary25 #IDW2025

RDA TIGER WGs Supported sessions

As part of International Data Week 2025

25th PLENARY MEETING

Simon Hodson and 11 others

Research Data Alliance Europe
1,294 followers
2mo • 🌐

Read the latest **Research Data Alliance (RDA) Adoption Stories**, exploring how the Global Open Research Commons (GORC) Model has been used by the community.

REASON Project
Learn how the REASON (ResEARch CommonS for Norway) used the GORC International Model as a conceptual framework to align their proposal for a national infrastructure in Norway with internationally recognised standards and recommendations.
https://lnkd.in/e2e_5gS9

SURF
Explore how SURF used the GORC Model to tackle the lack of clarity and consistency when discussing "infrastructure" in research contexts.
<https://ow.ly/iWP250WXwh3>

These Adoption Stories were collected and published with support from the RDA TIGER Project.

Adoption Stories
Adopting the Global Open Research Commons (GORC) Model

Supported by the RDA TIGER Project

Liise Lehtsalu and 15 others 5 reposts

Figures 7, 8, 9. Left to right: Social media promotion of RDA WG meeting, RDA TIGER-supported WG sessions at RDA Plenaries, supported WG adoption story

Newsletters

To avoid duplication and content fatigue, it was decided to use the RDA global monthly newsletters³³ for all RDA TIGER-related updates, both at the high level and for supported WG activity promotion. WGs with Statements of Work in community review and kick off meetings (C1), various updates during the main working period as well as WG-related events (C2), and final output promotion (C3) were highlighted monthly in these newsletters. The decision to use the RDA newsletter leveraged a global audience of 16,000 subscribers, while also highlighting the European strategic focus of RDA TIGER. An

³³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/news-stories/newsletters/>

RDA TIGER "Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions" is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0 Project: 101094406.

extensive list showcasing how WP2 leveraged the RDA newsletter to continuously promote all supported-WG content in these newsletters is provided in Annex 1.

Exhibition tables

Where appropriate, RDA TIGER also participated in events and conferences through exhibition tables.

Figures 10 & 11. RDA TIGER exhibition table at RDA Plenary 23 in Costa Rica, November 2024, featuring event collaterals, GORC IM WG printed communiques, RDA Knowledge Base Demo booth

Figures 12 & 13. Joint exhibition table at EOSC Symposium 2023 showcasing RDA TIGER, WorldFAIR and EOSC Future/RDA Domain Ambassador programme

Primarily this type of activity took place at RDA Plenaries (figures 10 & 11), but networking opportunities were also leveraged at the EOSC Symposium 2023 (figures 12 & 13), EGI2024 joint interoperability booth

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0 Project: 101094406.

with FAIR IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC^{34 35} and at the International Digital Curation Conference (IDCC) 2025^{36 37} alongside an RDA TIGER poster and lightning talk presentation.

Event collaterals

The updated RDA TIGER toolkit³⁸ provides an overview of collaterals created for distribution at events, in particular at RDA Plenaries. As mentioned above, content developed specifically for WGs - white papers, infographics, communiques - was also printed and distributed to attendees at events.

Posters

Poster presentations at key stakeholder events across Europe were used as an important communication and engagement tool, presenting the work of WGs relevant to each event audience. These raised awareness about the project and services available to RDA WGs, and helped to convey that those external to RDA communities could also use the RDA platform to further refine, expand and internationalise their work. RDA TIGER posters are available on the project Zenodo community³⁹.

Webinars

WP2 organised multiple webinar series under the following four categories:

- RDA TIGER cross-fertilisation webinar series organised thematically and in alignment SRIA implementation challenge areas, during which related RDA TIGER-supported WGs presented their outputs and recommendations⁴⁰.
- RDA Europe regional webinar series, aiming to engage European national networks and showcase RDA outputs of particular national interest (following WP2 consultation with national representatives).
- RDA TIGER open call and cascade grant informational webinars⁴¹.
- RDA Knowledge Base (KB) launch webinars and hands-on workshops⁴².

The full list of webinars organised by WP2 is presented in Annex 1.

Interviews

³⁴ <https://www.egi.eu/article/meet-egi2024-exhibitors-fair-impact-rda-tiger-faircore4eosc/>

³⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/on-the-way-to-data-interoperability-reflections-on-the-egi-2024/>

³⁶ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/rda-europe_idcc25-rdatiger-activity-7297527397027885056-7B4N?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAABW_nuoBWTZD2D7FByfXzGNKvdUQoNI_ZZQ

³⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/soft-infrastructure-stronger-communities-rda-europe-in-action-during-idcc25-and-fairfest/>

³⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14500639>

³⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/rda-tiger/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10>

⁴⁰ https://www.rd-alliance.org/events/?_keyword=CROSS-FERTILISATION

⁴¹ https://www.rd-alliance.org/events/?_keyword=rda%20tiger%20open%20call%20

⁴² https://www.rd-alliance.org/events/?_keyword=knowledge%20base

RDA TIGER grantees across all support types present in International Data Week 2025 (IDW2025) in Brisbane, Australia in October 2025 were invited to highlight the ways RDA TIGER contributed to their work as well as their most important achievements in RDA. The interviews are available on the RDA Europe Youtube channel⁴³, the RDA website and also highlighted on social media⁴⁴.

Mailing lists

News items and events were circulated in mailing lists available to the consortium through the RDA website (e.g., regional mailing lists) as well as RDA organisational member and partner lists (e.g., Digital Curation Centre (DCC) associates mailing list), and other lists reaching out to national networks.

EOSC Forum

The 'EOSC News' section of the EOSC Forum was also leveraged for the promotion of RDA TIGER events and webinars, aiming to further engage INFRA-EOSC projects and the EOSC ecosystem in general.

Direct communication

Direct outreach by email was also implemented by reaching out to communications officers within other projects or organisations with requests to cross-post and share specific content within their networks.

3. Service Implementation Highlights

This section expands on notable examples of communication campaigns and activities carried out throughout the project in terms of service and product awareness, specifically for WGs receiving support across lifecycle stages, as well as from the perspective of thematic contributions to EOSC.

3.1 RDA TIGER Cross fertilisation webinars

In order to showcase the direct alignment of the RDA TIGER-supported WGs to topics derived from implementation challenges and other cross-cutting issues in the EOSC SRIA, two series of cross-fertilisation webinars were organised featuring multiple RDA WGs. The webinars were organised aiming to facilitate knowledge exchange between WGs while also addressing key topics of interest in the EOSC ecosystem.

The topics of the webinars were:

⁴³ <https://youtu.be/T1xYt9HO6K0?si=bXbn2heQRKK6Jjd8n>

⁴⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7402724194557517824>

- [Semantic Interoperability](#) (November 2024)
- [\(Meta\)Data Standards](#) (December 2024)
- [FAIR/CARE/TRUST Principles adoption](#) (December 2024)
- [Making mappings FAIR](#) (November 2025)
- [Repositories, trustworthiness and certification](#) (December 2025)

The webinars enabled the alignment of RDA WGs on the topics presented, resulting in a number of collaborations. Following the webinar on Semantic Interoperability, the FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG will use the FAIR Mappings WG work on how to describe mappings into its recommendations for a minimal FAIR metadata schema for genomic annotations. The meetings also facilitated cross-fertilisation between RDA WGs and other European initiatives, specifically the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects⁴⁵ following the Repositories, trustworthiness and certification webinar in December 2025.

Results from the webinars also contributed to the report D3.6 - Landscape analysis on the value of RDA Outputs to EOSC⁴⁶.

3.2 RDA TIGER supported WG Plenary pre- and post- event campaigns

WP2 carried out intense pre- and post- RDA Plenary promotion, in addition to frequent updates on social media during plenaries, to increase Plenary participation, attract new membership and overall to amplify the efforts of the RDA TIGER supported WGs. Selected examples of these activities are provided below.

Figure 14. RDA TIGER WG Plenary sessions social media campaign at IDW2025

- [Upcoming TIGER-supported session campaigns, reminders and updates on Plenary days:](#)
 - RDA Plenary 25 TIGER session reminders on social media^{47 48}
- [Post Plenary wrap up blog:](#)

⁴⁵ <https://eden-fidelis.eu/>

⁴⁶ O'Connor, R., Grau, N., Lehtsalu, L., Claire, C., Delipalta, A., Hanahoe, H. (2025). D3.6: Landscape analysis on the value of RDA Outputs to EOSC. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

⁴⁷ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7383325138823393280>

⁴⁸ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7384004480477937664>

- [RDA Plenary 22: An overview of RDA TIGER-supported WGs, their sessions and progress.](#)
- [RDA Plenary 23: A summary update](#) of RDA TIGER-supported WGs; an overview of all TIGER WG sessions and the high level project session (fireside chat discussion adoption and impact); and a thematic analysis of the project, empowering groups to innovative solutions around topics such as semantic interoperability, (meta)data standards, FAIR adoption, and much more.
- [Highlights of activities happening in RDA TIGER WGs, the impact of their work, and how the community can get involved in shaping their outputs.](#)

3.3 Data for AI: From Readiness to Ethics - a panel discussion showcasing the RDA AIDV WG

In September 2025 RDA TIGER hosted a panel discussion at the Open Science FAIR 2025 in Geneva on the topic of ‘Data For AI: From Readiness to Ethics’⁴⁹. The panel was organised by RDA TIGER WP2 in support of the RDA Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation (AIDV) WG, which had by then released four Recommendations and a supporting output⁵⁰.

The panel was moderated by RDA TIGER and featured two AIDV WG co-chairs⁵¹. The discussion highlighted their publications, which includes detailed, implementable AI-related guidance on informed consent, ethical review, and a framework for an AI Bill of Rights.

Figure 15. Live polling results snapshot during ‘DATA for AI’ panel at OSFAIR 2025 featuring the RDA AIDV WG (presentation: Natalie Meyers)

⁴⁹ <https://www.opensciencefair.eu/panels/data-for-ai-from-readiness-to-ethics>

⁵⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/artificial-intelligence-and-data-visitation-aidv-wg/outputs/>

⁵¹

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/open-science-fair_openaire-osfair2025-cern-activity-7373741780334268416- DO?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAABW_nuoBWTZD2D7FBYfXzGNKvdUQoNI_ZZQ

The panel discussed the WG findings within the context of ongoing developments in the ethical, human rights, and regulatory contributions to AI governance in the European digital research environment. Particular reference was made to the European Commission's 'A European strategy for AI in science' within its overall AI Continent Action Plan.

The discussion touched on cross-border and cross-regional developments in AI governance with inclusion of the recent ACHRP's 'Study on human and people's rights and artificial intelligence, robotics, and other new and emerging technologies'. The session was very well received from the audience, showcasing an example of RDA WGs carrying out significant and highly relevant work for a range of European discussions including policy. The recording is publicly available on the CERN document server⁵².

3.4 The RDA Knowledge Base

Significant efforts were carried out in collaboration with RDA TIGER WP4 'Output Support Services' across all stages of development of the RDA Knowledge Base (KB). WP2 supported early dissemination during the testing and concept phases, facilitating the organisation of multiple webinars aiming to engage the community and explain the tool functionality, leading up to the beta launch and subsequent official launch. This was followed by the hands-on sessions which provided valuable information and guidance for users on using the KB in their day to day work, and the value of the tool for the findability of RDA outputs. These efforts were supplemented by organising demo stations at RDA Plenaries (see also section 2.5, figure 6 above) and presenting demos of the KB in multiple events and conferences across Europe. While this activity largely pertains to RDA TIGER high level dissemination of results, WP2 also supported the organisation of targeted hands-on sessions that would help supported WGs utilise the KB in their work and improve outputs and workflows.

Knowledge Base Webinar Series

- [The RDA Knowledge Base Beta Launch](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Hands-on & Feedback Session #1](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Hands-on & Feedback Session #2](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Workshop \(Morning Session\)](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Launch \(Afternoon Session\)](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Workshop \(Afternoon Session\)](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Launch \(Morning Session\)](#)

Knowledge Base event presentations and demos

⁵² <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2942779?ln=en>

- RDA Knowledge Base: One stop shop for all RDA outputs and resources at [OSFAIR 2025](#) and at [EGI2025](#)

Get to Know the RDA Knowledge Base information booklet

In December 2025, WP2 carried out a series of consultations with the WP4 development team and produced an information booklet⁵³ presenting the RDA KB in a community and user-friendly way, aiming to supplement the multiple technology focused campaigns that took place earlier in the project. This is a valuable resource that provides an explanation of terminology, takes the user through the process of using each feature, and explains how the tool aims to improve the quality, usefulness, and maintenance of RDA outputs, and to help users find, use, annotate, and publish RDA-related materials. WP2 put significant effort into supporting this project output, which also aims to support standardisation in RDA outputs and aligning these outputs with relevant policy in Europe, e.g. EOSC for example through the Working Group Guidelines, recommended metadata schema and RDA-specific vocabularies.

4. Performance Monitoring & Impact

4.1 KPIs and Target Outcomes: Definition & Tracking

The KPIs defined for WP2 were designed to assess the visibility, engagement, participation, and overall impact of the RDA TIGER Communication and Facilitation Service for each supported WG per lifecycle stage, as well as for project awareness and high level outreach. A detailed report on WP2 KPIs and their implementation and evolution through the course of the project is provided in D6.5, Section 4.2⁵⁴. For completeness, the list of activities per KPI is also provided in Annex 1; the reader is referred to D6.5 for the full analysis.

4.2 Analytics and impact

4.2.1 Website analytics

Website analytics play a central role in understanding and showcasing community engagement with RDA TIGER and increasing RDA WG visibility through activities providing higher website traffic. Because of the website migration from drupal to wordpress in early 2024, the shift to new web platform provider in late 2024 and the resulting website disruptions from March - September 2024, web statistics are not available for the first half of the project. However, data collected from October 2024 to December 2025 with the support of the new RDA website provider and a dedicated dashboard for RDA TIGER-related

⁵³ Sharma, C. J. M., Hugo, W., & Saldner, S. (2025). Getting to Know the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Knowledge Base (1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17882751>

⁵⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877446>

web content indicate very robust user interest and community engagement with the project. Figure 16 below presents a snapshot of web analytics across all RDA TIGER pages (i.e, pages on the RDA website that include 'rda-tiger' in the url) in the period October 2024 - December 2025, showing over 10,000 views for a period of 14 months. Key highlights include 4,446 total users, 3,084 new users, 8,235 sessions and 10,400 page views (figure 16).

Figure 16. Overview of user engagement on pages on RDA TIGER-related web pages on the RDA website

Figure 17. RDA TIGER user visits geographical distribution

Furthermore, geographical analytics highlight the strong international reach of RDA and the TIGER initiative, with visitors engaging from Europe, North America, Asia, and Africa. This demonstrates that TIGER activities effectively supported WG visibility not only within Europe but across the global research data community (figure 17).

The community’s continued engagement is also reflected in returning visitors who frequently revisited WG pages, particularly during key communication bursts aligned with WG milestones (figure 18). This showcases the clear community interest in the RDA TIGER project.

Figure 18. RDA TIGER new and returning user analytics for the period 9 October 2024 - 2025

As seen in figure 18 above, the RDA TIGER-related web content presented a spike in visits around RDA Plenary meetings, and the following dates and events:

- 13 March 2025 (106 new users): Potential correlation with announcement of RDA TIGER presence on BlueSky, or through the publication of the adoption story on RDA Common Descriptive Attributes of Research Data Repositories Recommendation⁵⁵ through RDA TIGER channels.

⁵⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/data-repository-attributes-wg/outputs/?output=94428>

- 14 July 2025 (109 new users): Launch of the 2nd RDA TIGER travel grant support for IDW2025 attendance⁵⁶.

4.2.2 Newsletter analytics

The RDA global newsletter remains one of the strongest channels for high-quality traffic. TIGER-related items consistently performed above the newsletter’s baseline click-through rate (CTR), confirming newsletter subscribers as a highly engaged audience.

As outlined in the previous section, before the migration to the current mailing infrastructure, newsletters were distributed via an internally developed Drupal-based system. For newsletters disseminated in 2023, only aggregated view counts are available, which limits the possibility of a more granular performance analysis (e.g., open rates or click-through rates).

Nevertheless, the available data indicate consistent visibility and sustained interest in newsletter content. View counts across 2023 newsletters typically ranged around 700 views per issue, indicating stable readership levels and regular exposure of project- and community-related content, including early RDA TIGER communications.

Figure 19. RDA Newsletter analytics, which included RDA TIGER featured updates for the period January 2024 - December 2025

⁵⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/rda-tiger-travel-grants-for-rda-plenary-25-2nd-call/>

During the reporting period for which full analytics are available, newsletter items related to RDA TIGER consistently performed above the overall newsletter baseline in terms of click-through rate, confirming the relevance of TIGER content for the RDA community.

Quantitative overview (January 2024 – 19 December 2025)

- Average open rate: **29.9%**
- Average click-through rate (CTR): **6.2%**
- Most clicked TIGER items: Event announcements and service-related updates

4.2.3 Social Media analytics

Social media activity, primarily via LinkedIn and X, played a critical role in driving awareness for WG milestones, outputs, and events. Both platforms serve distinct audiences, and the combined insight offers a holistic view of community response.

LinkedIn Performance

LinkedIn represents the primary social media channel used within RDA TIGER to reach the broader research data community and stakeholders across Europe and beyond.

Figures 20 & 21. RDA TIGER LinkedIn posts with the most interactions: 411 clicks and 1,200 impressions and 222 clicks and 1,326 impressions, respectively

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0 Project: 101094406.

The platform was used to disseminate project updates, promote events and services, and reinforce the visibility of RDA TIGER activities.

- Followers: 1295
- Posts analysed: 365
- Total impressions: 61,160
- Total clicks: 4,021
- Average engagement rate: 7.28% (strong for a professional audience)

The analysis of LinkedIn post engagement metrics shows a healthy balance of impressions and meaningful interactions. RDA TIGER-related posts, especially output announcements and cross-fertilisation webinars, consistently outperformed regular posts.

A sample of social media engagement during the promotional campaign at IDW2025 is presented below.

Table 5. Sample social media engagement analysis during IDW2025

Post	Impressions	Clicks	Likes	Comments	Reposts
Wrap-up post showcasing all RDA TIGER highlights and supported sessions at IDW2025	1205	411	64	1	7
Post promoting day 4 sessions of RDA TIGER-supported WGs	661	16	14	0	1
Post promoting day 3 sessions of RDA TIGER-supported WGs.	330	17	12	0	0
Post showcasing the RDA TIGER impact presentation during a plenary session at IDW2025	682	60	14	0	3
Post highlighting RDA TIGER posters at IDW2025	500	47	15	1	1
Post highlighting the beta version of the interactive web interface for the GORC International Model (IM), funded through the RDA TIGER Cascading Grants scheme, was	556	25	8	0	4

Post	Impressions	Clicks	Likes	Comments	Reposts
presented during International Data Week (IDW).					
Post promoting day 1 sessions of RDA TIGER-supported WGs.	777	13	16	0	2
Wrap-up post showcasing all RDA TIGER highlights and supported sessions at IDW2025	1205	411	64	1	7

X/Twitter Performance

- Followers: 5,947
- New followers: -434 (reflecting the overall sector trend due to platform instability 2023–2025)
- Engagement rate: 3.81%
- Total impressions: 35,566

Despite a decline in net followers (which is a common pattern across research organisations), engagement rates remained relatively strong. Posts tied to RDA Plenaries and WG output releases received the most engagement.

Bluesky Performance

The [RDA Europe Bluesky account](#) launched in late 2024 in response to the decline of Twitter/X and following the departure of other European stakeholders from the platform. The account, while not used as the main social media platform for the project, had consistent activity with 97 followers, 53 posts, and a limited level of interaction, with a total of 72 likes, 30 reposts, and 5 quote posts. These modest engagement levels are consistent with the early stages of adoption of Bluesky as a dissemination channel. Nevertheless, reposts and quotes indicate qualitative engagement, suggesting interest in content shared. Given the current scale of the platform and the absence of comprehensive analytics (e.g. impressions or engagement rates), Bluesky is considered an exploratory and complementary channel, supporting visibility and presence rather than serving as a primary dissemination outlet.

4.2.4 Webinar analytics

Attendance at RDA TIGER webinars ranged at approximately 50% of total registrations; this pattern has been observed frequently in recent years across projects and activities, as online event fatigue often drives the audience to register for meetings in order to gain access to post-event recording and material dissemination. As seen in table 6 below, the cross-fertilisation webinar series had consistent attendance in the range of 30 - 40 attendees per session.

Table 6. Sample of webinar participation in the period October 2025 - December 2025

Webinar	Participants
RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinar: Semantic Interoperability	40
RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinar: FAIR/TRUST/CARE Adoption	30
RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinar: (Meta)Data Standards	30
RDA TIGER Call for Facilitation launch webinar (2023)	n/a
RDA TIGER Cascade Grants Informational Webinar (2024)	18
The RDA in the Baltics	75
RDA in Denmark	16
The RDA Knowledge Base Beta Launch	47
RDA TIGER Cascading Grants Informational Webinar (2025)	28
RDA Knowledge Base Hands-on & Feedback Session #2	15
RDA Knowledge Base Hands-on & Feedback Session #1	10
RDA Knowledge Base Launch (morning session)	20
RDA Knowledge Base Launch (afternoon session)	20
RDA Knowledge Base Hands-on session (morning session)	25
RDA Knowledge Base Hands-on session (afternoon session)	29
RDA TIGER Cross-fertilisation webinar series:	31

Webinar	Participants
Repositories, trustworthiness and certification	
RDA TIGER cross-fertilisation webinar series: Making mappings FAIR	37

4.2.5. Reflections on impact of communication activities

The impact of WP2 activities is measurable in various ways, some apparent within WP2 and many by looking across WPs and the project as a whole. In terms of impact directly related to WP2, the progress against set KPIs (Annex 1) in combination to the highly positive analytics presented in this section highlight that the multi-faceted communication efforts succeeded in stimulating the broader research data community and engaging the target audiences with project-related activities, as shown for example by the high numbers for new and returning users to RDA TIGER-related content on the website and over 10,000 page views in a period of 14 months. The overall high and sustained engagement across communications channels indicates successful project awareness campaigns, as also showcased by the high number of applications submitted on the continuously open calls for support (D1.4, section 1⁵⁷; D6.5⁵⁸, sections 4.1 and 4.5).

The RDA TIGER engagement of RDA regional communities in combination to leveraging other HE projects and related stakeholders in Europe (e.g., LIBER, EGI, EUDAT, OpenAIRE, DCC) helped expand amplification efforts outwith the immediate RDA membership, and resulted in impact that is also measurable by looking at KPIs outside of WP2. In particular, D6.5⁵⁹ (section 4.3, figure 8) reports on new RDA members joining RDA TIGER-supported WGs and notes 15% of WG members on average after WGs were onboarded on the project (stages C2 and C3) being new to RDA, and 25% for WGs supported from the outset (C1). It is plausible to suggest that the consistent and sustained WG activity promotion by the TIGER communication team, in combination with all other support activities, contributed to this increase in membership and to attracting new members to the RDA community.

⁵⁷ Lehtsalu, L., & Delipalta, A. (2025). RDA TIGER D1.4: Final report on the external and direct support provision and lessons learned. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17876865>

⁵⁸ O'Connor, R., Grau, N., Saldner, S., Minichiello, F., Lehtsalu, L., Delipalta, A. (2025) RDA TIGER D6.5: Final quality evaluation report on the RDA TIGER WG services. Zenodo. <https://10.5281/zenodo.17877446>

⁵⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877446>

4.3 Working Group Feedback and Satisfaction

The RDA TIGER feedback collection process and result analysis is presented in detail in D6.5⁶⁰. 35 responses were received to the project feedback survey⁶¹, of which 4 related to the communication service. 2 of these responses were from the Pilot Demonstrator WGs receiving dedicated communication support, and 2 were received from the WGs primarily receiving facilitation support.

From the WGs receiving dedicated support, in response to the answer ‘Overall, how satisfied are you with the RDA TIGER service you have received/are receiving?’ the WGs indicated that they were ‘very satisfied’. When asked to provide more details about the nature of the service they received, they responded that collaterals (white papers, communiques, infographics) developed by WP2 and staff were ‘very helpful gathering our requirements and producing a white paper and infographic, which were very useful in promoting the group and the outputs’, that the ‘infographic made the checklist more user friendly and visual’, and that the materials ‘produced very useful materials to give people as a quick reference’. Both respondents indicated that the service is valuable for RDA WGs, with a comment that ‘It’s a valuable service for promoting WG outputs and linking up commonalities across different RDA groups’.

From the 2 communications-related responses coming from WGs primarily receiving facilitation support, the first one indicated that they were ‘satisfied’ with the service, and answered ‘Yes’ to the question of whether it is a valuable initiative for RDA WGs, with no further comment. The second response from this category indicated satisfaction with RDA TIGER personnel, but noted that tools, effort and infrastructure available to staff should be increased, as well as the ability to use more expansive functionality in terms of meeting organisation and scheduling that what was available to the project. This feedback was primarily in response to the functionality available to the RDA TIGER team as part of established RDA infrastructure; it refers to the period of the transition and migration to the new platform, at a time when the RDA community was dealing with significant change, including a temporary freeze on the RDA website and process updates to the web-based communications with WG members. As outlined in D6.5, the RDA TIGER team supported the community through this transition period and provided significant support to co-chairs and WG members, communicating their issues and concerns to RDA Secretariat and the website development team, and relaying updates outside those regularly provided to the wider RDA community.

⁶⁰ O’Connor, R., Grau, N., Saldner, S., Minichiello, F., Lehtsalu, L., Delipalta, A. (2025) D6.5: Final quality evaluation report on the RDA TIGER WG services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877446>

⁶¹

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfOVdsxSh7Gjvx30lthtDGREQHqTlztJxaSpcOxbEJHHPDVQ/viewform>

5. Stakeholder engagement overview

Table 7 below presents the high-level stakeholders identified both for the project as a whole (service platform) and for the communication service offered to WGs in particular at project initiation, and provides an update with corresponding indicative actions and fora by which these groups were engaged.

Table 7. RDA TIGER stakeholders

Stakeholder	Connection to RDA TIGER	Communication Channels identified at project initiation	Indicative activities and fora used in response to stakeholder engagement plan
RDA Membership	Target audience of RDA TIGER, benefits from high quality WG Outputs and efficient meetings. Potential adopters of Group Outputs exist in this stakeholder group.	RDA Global and EU channels (web platform, Plenaries, social media, other RDA events). Targeted engagement of membership sub-groups depending on supported WG bespoke strategies and needs as defined in discussions with co-chairs.	RDA website, RDA TIGER dedicated webspace, RDA AISBL social media channels (multiple), RDA Global social media channels, website group posting functionality, RDA Plenary outreach, RDA Plenary exhibition booths, active TIGER participation in Plenaries through organisation of sessions (community adoption feedback session at RDA P24 , contribution to RDA impact and adoption session at P23 , ‘When the RDA TIGER roars’ presentation, part of the global impact session at P25).
RDA Group co-chairs	Main target audience of RDA TIGER services, benefits from in-kind support and direct grants.	RDA Global channels (web platform, Plenaries, social media, other RDA events).	As above, in addition to direct outreach and communication between co-chairs and TIGER staff

Stakeholder	Connection to RDA TIGER	Communication Channels identified at project initiation	Indicative activities and fora used in response to stakeholder engagement plan
RDA Governance	The Governance structure has direct interest into the testing (and success) of the RDA TIGER model due to the potential for it developing into a paid service for the RDA. Better supported WGs also result in more professionalised RDA processes and Outputs, which aligns with the current RDA Strategic plan.	Direct engagement.	Meetings every two weeks with RDA Secretariat, participation in RDA Regional Advisory Board and Regional Assembly through RDA AISBL (European regional partner), attendance at RDA Funders Forum meetings at Plenaries, attendance at RDA TAB meets co-chairs meetings.
Funder's Forum	The Funders' Forum provides potential WG Output adopters from funding organisations.	Virtual meetings, Plenaries, direct engagement if a Funder is identified as stakeholder for a supported WG.	Attendance at Funder's Forum meetings at Plenaries.
Industry	The new RDA framework for Industry collaborations creates a pathway for engaging the public sector; apart from this being of interest for WGs as being a pool of potential adopters, the recent collaboration with Oracle creates a link for privately facilitated/funded Groups within RDA,	Plenaries, exhibition booths at third party events, targeted engagement, social media.	Plenaries, European events and conferences.

Stakeholder	Connection to RDA TIGER	Communication Channels identified at project initiation	Indicative activities and fora used in response to stakeholder engagement plan
	which is of interest to RDA TIGER from a sustainability and exploitation perspective.		
EOSC Community	The EOSC community provides potential WG Output adopters at a higher level; more specifically, EOSC is a critical stakeholder given the strict requirement for supported WGs to align with its priorities and objectives.	EOSC Focus, EOSC Forum, HE WG, events (e.g., EOSC Symposium, direct engagement)	Attendance at all EOSC Winter Schools, EOSC Symposia and EOSC General Assemblies, EOSC Horizon Europe Communication and Technical WGs, exploration of collaboration opportunities within EOSC Focus, submitted proposals to present lightning talks or posters at EOSC symposia.
ESFRI / Cluster projects	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and European channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events,	Direct targeting of ESFRIs did not take place; instead, a chapter outlining the value of RDA for ESFRIs is included in D3.6 ⁶² to support future engagement based on concrete resources.
Individual Researchers & Research Communities	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise	RDA Global and European channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other	In addition to leveraging planned channels, the RDA TIGER team attended multiple

⁶² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

Stakeholder	Connection to RDA TIGER	Communication Channels identified at project initiation	Indicative activities and fora used in response to stakeholder engagement plan
	from which RDA can draw.	events, WG contacts, direct engagement.	events across Europe advocating for the value of RDA outputs ⁶³ .
(e-)Research Infrastructures	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and European channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, direct engagement.	As above.
Research funders	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and European channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, exhibition booths, direct engagement.	In addition to leveraging planned channels, the RDA TIGER coordinators alongside the RDA Secretary General attended meetings with the Head of Unit at the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) discussing global RDA developments and specific impact in Europe.
Data Stewards and Research support staff	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and European channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, direct engagement.	In addition to leveraging planned channels, presentations and attendance of national data Stewardship events in Italy and Ireland.

⁶³ See also D2.3: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775225>

Stakeholder	Connection to RDA TIGER	Communication Channels identified at project initiation	Indicative activities and fora used in response to stakeholder engagement plan
Policymakers	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and European channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, exhibition booths, direct engagement.	In addition to leveraging planned channels and meetings with DG RTD referenced above, RDA TIGER WP2 developed specific content intended for policy makers for the GORC IM WG, and contributed to the RDA for Policy white paper series .
Research institutions	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and European channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, direct engagement.	Events and conferences, social media channels.
Open Science / Research Clouds / Commons	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and European channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, direct engagement.	Events and conferences, social media channels.
Repositories/archives	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and European channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, direct engagement.	In addition to planned means, attendance of specific relevant events (e.g., International Digital Curation Conference).
Research software Engineers / software	Potential WG Recommendation and	RDA Global and European channels, web	Audience primarily engaged through the

Stakeholder	Connection to RDA TIGER	Communication Channels identified at project initiation	Indicative activities and fora used in response to stakeholder engagement plan
developers	Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, direct engagement.	PRO4RS WG membership and related facilitation activities.

5.1 Engagement with the RDA Community

RDA TIGER utilised various ways to engage with the community more directly and in an interactive way, beyond the planned day-to-day outreach and engagement, and beyond the service support provided to the WGs. RDA Plenary-related activities, webinars, and social media channels used have been summarised in the Annex in response to KPIs and also in section 4. The particular focus of RDA TIGER WP2 on engagement of regional networks has been analysed in D2.3 Report on the progress of European national network engagement in RDA TIGER WGs⁶⁴. This report will present two engagement activities in particular that should be highlighted in order to demonstrate the commitment of RDA TIGER to to interact with stakeholders across Europe, and to support the RDA community in showcasing and leveraging the impact of its work.

Community insights on use, adoption and impact of RDA Outputs at RDA Plenary 24

First, at the RDA Virtual Plenary 24 in April 2025, the RDA TIGER project held a session ‘Community insights on use, adoption and impact of RDA Outputs’⁶⁵ to gather community feedback on how RDA Group outputs are used and the factors affecting their uptake, in order to gain understanding and further support the adoption and implementation of RDA outputs. This session contributed to the early development stages of the report ‘D3.6 - Landscape analysis on the value of RDA Outputs to EOSC’⁶⁶, and a full analysis of results is included D3.6 Annex 5.

⁶⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775225>

⁶⁵ A recording of the session is available on Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BkMiGDscII0> ; a link to the slidedeck used can be found on the RDA VP24 programme page: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/p24/programme-24/>

⁶⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

Figure 22. Mentimeter presentation at RDA Plenary 24 TIGER-organised adoption session

RDA in Europe Summit

The second community engagement landmark in RDA TIGER showcasing the efforts to engage the RDA regional networks, but also adopters of RDA all across Europe was the RDA in Europe Summit⁶⁷ in November 2025. The event also served as the final meeting of RDA TIGER with presentations from RDA TIGER-supported WGs, as well as the final project impact session⁶⁸ highlighting the mapping of RDA outputs to the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), European project space, National Open Science Strategies and the Knowledge Base carried out by the project.

The Summit invited submissions for lightning talks and projects from use cases and adopters in Europe across the various RDA stakeholder groups (libraries, industry, research performing organisations, funders, etc), regional network representatives outwith and within RDA, and Horizon Europe projects. The event was hosted by CNRS and RDA France, co-organised with RDA Europe and RDA TIGER WP2, and brought together 70 attendees from 15 European countries and featured representation from the EOSC Steering Board⁶⁹, research infrastructures (ENVRI and Finish Meteorological Institute), other community organisations (LIBER⁷⁰), national open science networks (The Hellenic Open Science Initiative ‘HOSI’⁷¹ and

⁶⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/events/rda-europe-annual-summit/>

⁶⁸ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7396472670990524416>

⁶⁹ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7396522185001152512>

⁷⁰ <https://libereurope.eu/>

⁷¹ <https://www.hellenicopenscience.gr/el/>

NDFI⁷²), Horizon Europe-funded projects (OSTrails⁷³, FAIR-IMPACT⁷⁴, EOSC-RAISE⁷⁵, FIDELIS⁷⁶), multiple European RDA regional representatives and RDA TIGER grantees (Building Immune Digital Twins⁷⁷ supported WG, FAIRMap4ART⁷⁸ cascade grantee, Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools (MaLDReTH) WG⁷⁹ use case).

The event culminated in five parallel breakout sessions exploring the role of RDA in progressing the adoption of RDA outputs in support of addressing the most frequently occurring policy areas identified in the mapping of RDA outputs to National Open Science Policies carried out in D3.6.

5.2 EOSC ecosystem & Broader European Community

RDA TIGER embarked on a journey to advocate the value of the supported WGs and the RDA community across Europe. D2.3 Report on the progress of European national network engagement in RDA TIGER WGs⁸⁰ provided a comprehensive analysis of engagement at social fora across Europe, starting from RDA regions to other European national Open Science networks, EOSC-related events at the national, project and EOSC Association levels, as well as other like-minded initiatives in the European research data space. As outlined in the aforementioned report, these activities intended to increase engagement with the RDA, increase adoption and implementation of outputs in the region, inform the broader European community about the role of RDA in the internationalisation of European achievements and engage the wider ecosystem with the RDA TIGER project and the available support making it easier for these external communities to start an RDA WG during the project lifetime.

5.3 Cross-Project Synergies

The RDA TIGER WP2 engaged with other HE projects that aligned with the overall objectives of the project, or where synergies with supported WGs were identified.

All roads lead to Interoperability: FAIR-IMPACT, RDA TIGER and FAIRCORE4EOSC

⁷² <https://www.nfdi.de/>

⁷³ <https://ostrails.eu/>

⁷⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/>

⁷⁵ <https://raise-science.eu/the-project/>

⁷⁶ <https://eden-fidelis.eu/>

⁷⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/building-immune-digital-twins-wg/activity>

⁷⁸

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/driving-open-science-and-interoperability-through-rda-tiger-cascade-grants-me-et-the-second-wave-of-grant-awardees/>

⁷⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-ofr-mapping-landscape-digital-research-tools-wg/activity>

⁸⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775225>

In September 2024 RDA TIGER WP2 teamed up with FAIRCORE4EOSC⁸¹ and FAIR IMPACT with a joint interoperability booth at EGI2024⁸², leveraging the common objective across the three projects working towards supporting and promoting interoperability mechanisms across domains and institutions and foster a global alignment of FAIR frameworks.

With FAIR-IMPACT focusing on enabling the FAIR principles for EOSC across scientific communities, stakeholder groups and research outputs at a European, national and institutional level, RDA TIGER supporting the Research Data Alliance community and WGs that concretely align, harmonise and standardise Open Science developments, and FAIRCORE4EOSC working on on the development and realisation of core components for the EOSC, the exhibition booth highlighted the significant efforts to streamline data interoperability across borders and research domains in support of SRIA and the EOSC Interoperability Framework⁸³.

RDA TIGER cross-fertilisation activities with EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS

The second webinar part of the 2025 RDA TIGER cross-fertilisation series focused on ‘Repositories, trustworthiness and certification’. The event focused on presentations from the RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption Working Group and the Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG)⁸⁴, highlighting the work that is taking place within these WGs regarding repository trustworthiness and certification processes. The webinar featured presentations from EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS aligning their outputs with work carried out by the TIGER-supported WGs and highlighting their complementarity. Moreover, the EDEN-FIDELIS Bootcamps took place in November 2025, co-located with the final RDA TIGER meeting at the RDA in Europe Summit⁸⁵.

EOSC Data Commons Adoption Story materials and promotion

⁸¹ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

⁸² <https://www.egi.eu/article/meet-egi2024-exhibitors-fair-impact-rda-tiger-faircore4eosc/>

⁸³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/on-the-way-to-data-interoperability-reflections-on-the-egi-2024/>

⁸⁴

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/community-based-catalogue-requirements-trustworthy-technical-repository-service-providers/activity>

⁸⁵

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/events/rda-tiger-cross-fertilisation-webinar-series-repositories-trustworthiness-and-certification/>

With the support of the RDA TIGER projects as part of its dedicated communication support provision to the GORC initiative, the EOSC Data Commons⁸⁶ project completed an adoption story describing its work on implementing the GORC Typology and Definitions⁸⁷.

6. Communications Materials & Resources

6.1 Evolved use of Branding

Over the course of the RDA TIGER project, the visual identity and communications materials used to support WGs evolved towards a unified branded suite of digital and print templates. This evolution was guided by the need to ensure coherence across all RDA TIGER communications, support user recognition, and simplify the production of visually appealing and accessible materials for a growing number of WGs and stakeholders. The developed templates shared the core branding with the new RDA global designs and communication toolkit to further align the project with the mission and visual identity of the RDA, and to ensure sustainability and reusability of materials post-funding period.

In addition to the TIGER-specific assets outlined in D2.1: Communications Toolkit (which included a PowerPoint template, a set of simple graphics, business cards, and leaflets/flyers, as well as designs for promotional badges, notebooks, and water bottles), branded social media assets were designed (figures 23, 24). In the early stages of the project, social media assets were developed on a case-by-case basis. While these fulfilled immediate needs, they sometimes lacked consistency in style, colour palette, typography, or alignment with the overarching brand frameworks.

Figure 23 & 24. Examples of early project social media assets

⁸⁶ <https://www.eosc-data-commons.eu/>

⁸⁷

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/adoption-stories/adopting-the-global-open-research-commons-model-the-case-of-eos-c-data-commons/>

Figures 25 & 26 Examples of updated project social media assets

It became clear that a more systematic approach to branding was needed to improve efficiency, professionalism, and visual recognition across all channels. In response, WP2 initiated the creation of a cohesive visual identity for RDA TIGER social media assets (figures 25, 26).

The evolution of RDA TIGER branding and templates reflects a broader trend within the project: moving from flexible experimentation to structured, professionalised service delivery. The result was a recognisable and trusted visual identity that amplified the visibility and credibility of WGs and their outputs - a legacy that can be reused and built upon in future initiatives and by the RDA itself.

7. Reflections and lessons learned

The RDA TIGER communication service started in 2023 with two impactful pilot demonstrators at WG end stage and ambitious KPIs. In the first year of the project WP2 focused on building project awareness in order to ensure sufficient uptake of the services on offer - a successful endeavour as showcased by KPIs and overall popularity of the services. This section reflects on the evolution of the service, lessons learned in the process, and also considers the foundations, resources and synergies that need to be in place for such a communications service to succeed in future related endeavours.

Project awareness, high level engagement and outreach activities

- With regards to project awareness and uptake, beyond the credit claimed by the WP2 for the level of engagement shown by the community with the project, it became clear that support

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0 Project: 101094406.

provided by RDA TIGER across services is needed and valuable for a community composed of volunteers.

- Any communication service - whether integrated in a suite of multiple services or standalone - requires collaboration with the core of RDA operational management, the RDA Secretariat. Communications activities in support of an organisation require unified branding, global coordination to ensure content is aligned with the overall mission and objectives and timed appropriately to avoid overloading the audience with information or creating content fatigue. The RDA TIGER project ensured this alignment was in place by assigning a dedicated RDA Secretariat liaison from WP2 that maintained oversight of communication activities across global and European/TIGER channels.
- The broad range of communication and outreach activities succeeded in reaching multiple distinct stakeholders; it created an engaged and enthusiastic micro-community within RDA, while maintaining a clear RDA identity and without fragmenting the WGs between supported vs not supported groups. Clear communication across multiple channels and formats meant a service suite that was accessible to all WGs and membership.

Dedicated WG communication service provision

- KPIs drafted at the Grant Agreement (GA) stage and later reiterated in D2.2 intended to increase engagement by inventing new ways to provide internal and external communication support to RDA WGs. While the intention was to increase productivity and impact, when the project moved to the implementation stage it was evident that many of the KPIs were redundant or unrealistic and not in alignment with WG needs or processes. Examples of such KPIs are WG-internal newsletters and weekly WG-related content promotion. As explained in D6.5 section on WP2 KPI reporting, each WG progresses at a different pace, making the creation of weekly content for publication difficult and unnecessary. In future similar initiatives, WG specific KPIs should ensure realistic alignment with RDA processes, and focus on impact and implementation rather than general content generation (an approach eventually adopted by RDA TIGER WP2).
- Communication, outreach and facilitation support activities are very closely intertwined, and during the lifetime of the project and as the portfolio of supported WGs was increasing, the lines between the two services became less clear, resulting in parts of the communication service being delivered by facilitators (acting under WP2). By 2024, there was a natural division between what can be described as outward-facing marketing activities (carried out by communications personnel) and internal, direct communication/WG engagement activities (facilitators and project coordination acting under WP2). A clear example of such activities with blurred lines - not only between WP2 and WP5 but also WP3 - was outreach to potential new members and co-chairs at WG initiation stage, where the volume of close interactions between co-chairs and facilitators, the support facilitation provided to WG's with regards to scope definition and the

very intense engagement of WP5 in WG day to day meant that facilitators were best placed and most efficient in carrying out this activity. This intense involvement of facilitators with WG work also provided them with the required oversight to coordinate communication support requests between WGs and the communications service. While a balance was eventually achieved between project staff and the intended tasks were carried out, working cross-WPs was occasionally challenging. Early in the project it was decided to treat the facilitation service as the core in-kind support offering of the RDA TIGER and the entry-point to the rest of the in-kind support services. This decision contributed to the increase in responsibility placed on the facilitators. Future direct WG communication support services should consider integration with facilitation support from the beginning, rather than acting as separate stand alone services. This predefined correlation will help in expectation management and time planning for those delivering the service. Marketing tasks and high level communication support remains appropriate as a separate offering.

RDA TIGER: A European initiative for global cooperation

- As part of the project's direct outreach activities in support of WGs achieving the international composition of their co-chairs, the project received positive feedback from other RDA regions with regards to the global reach and engagement of RDA TIGER. This highlights the importance of support activities like RDA TIGER towards the internationalisation of results, and towards supporting a large, global community like the RDA.
- The communications campaigns and materials produced in support of WGs in Europe have been very positively received by the community, with other RDA regions stating that RDA TIGER serves as an example and benchmark for the type of communication strategy that could be replicated for the benefit of each region. The positive reaction of the international community reinforces the value of initiatives like RDA TIGER for regional impact.

8. Conclusion

The communication service worked across multiple levels of project and service awareness, offering targeted stakeholder engagement and a flexible, bespoke and adaptable service to RDA WGs. This approach contributed to the overall high uptake of RDA TIGER across the service suite, the high KPI success and ultimately, the increased visibility of the value of the global RDA outputs to the EOSC ecosystem. Across many communication channels and pathways, WP2 delivered a wealth of activities, including in person events, webinars, cross-fertilisation activities among RDA and other European initiatives and TIGER-supported panel discussions on key policy topics. The three years of the project also provided the RDA with a portfolio of communications reusable digital resources and lessons learned that can be easily adopted by future iterations of communication support services to RDA WGs. RDA TIGER

WP2 concludes having received praise from the community, even as far as being described as a benchmark and example of a communication strategy to be replicated by similar initiatives across RDA regions.

Annex 1. WP2 Key Performance Indicator report

A1.2 Project wide KPIs - service awareness

KPI WP2a Number of events at which RDA TIGER is presented

Description: Presentation of RDA TIGER in third party events during the project lifetime

Target: 5

Result: 15+⁸⁸

Comments: This KPI covers conferences, plenaries, and other third party events. The KPI was met and surpassed, as WP2 set out to present the TIGER activities across Europe with the intention of increasing the membership of the WGs and RDA in general by disseminating outside of the existing RDA community, and engaging with as many relevant stakeholders as possible beyond the immediate RDA membership.

KPI WP2b Number of webinars held around open calls per year of the project

Description: Webinars / drop-in sessions held around RDA TIGER Open Calls

Target: 3

Result: 6 (total)

2023:

- [RDA TIGER Call for Facilitation First Informational Webinar](#)
- [RDA TIGER Call for Facilitation Second Informational Webinar](#)
- [RDA TIGER Call for Facilitation Third Informational Webinar](#)

2024:

- [RDA TIGER Cascade Grants 2024 Informational Webinar](#)
- [RDA TIGER Drop-In Session For Open Call Application Support](#)

2025:

- [RDA TIGER Cascade Grants 2025 Informational Webinar](#)

Comments: During the first year of the project, as per KPI expectation, 3 informational webinars were held. In subsequent years, and based on existing high demand for RDA TIGER services, established, unchanged processes for RDA TIGER application submissions, existing recordings of informational material, offline advice and information provision by the TIGER team, and most importantly, the overall establishment of the RDA TIGER project as an initiative, 2 webinars were held in 2024 and 1 in 2025. By 2025, RDA TIGER had been integrated in RDA and the support on offer was widely known by the community.

⁸⁸ See RDA TIGER D2.3: Report on the progress of European national network engagement in RDA TIGER WGs Annex 1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775225>

KPI WP2c Numbers of webinars held around other initiatives per year of the project

Description: Webinars / drop-in sessions held around other RDA TIGER-related initiatives

Target: 3

Result: 23 (total)

2023

- [New RDA working group on Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities \(SSH\) - kick off meeting](#)
- [New RDA Working Group on Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data - kick off meeting](#)
- [Data Representation in Chemistry and Materials WG - kick-off meeting](#)
- [New RDA working group on FAIRification of genome sequence annotations \(tracks\) - Kickoff meetings in September](#)

2024

- [RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinar Series – Semantic Interoperability](#)
- [RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinar Series – \(Meta\)Data Standards](#)
- [From policy to implementation technologies | The EOSC-FUTURE/RDA AIDV-WG’s outputs framing Lifetime Omics data visitation technologies](#)
- [RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinar Series – FAIR/TRUST/CARE Adoption](#)
- [The state of Open Science in Slovenia](#)

2025

- [The RDA Knowledge Base Beta Launch](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Hands-on & Feedback Session #1](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Hands-on & Feedback Session #2](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Workshop \(Morning Session\)](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Launch \(Afternoon Session\)](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Workshop \(Afternoon Session\)](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Launch \(Morning Session\)](#)
- [RDA in the Baltics Webinar](#)
- [RDA in Denmark](#)
- RDA and the Polish Data Community ([post](#) and slides for the event: Lehtsalu, L. (2025, June 30). *RDA and the Polish Data Community*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15773023>)
- [RDA in Ireland: RDA Groups showcase](#)
- [RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinar Series – Making mappings FAIR](#)
- [RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinar Series – Repositories, trustworthiness and certification](#)
- [RDA in Europe Summit \(event in which final outputs and achievements of RDA TIGER were presented\)](#)

Comments: This KPI was met by organising numerous webinars around RDA TIGER initiatives. Specifically: 1) a series of cross-fertilisation webinars thematically organised which brought together various TIGER-supported WGs, 2) webinars supporting the kick-off of new RDA WGs in order to attract members, 3) events introducing the RDA Knowledge Base and collecting feedback on the tool, and 4) a series of regional webinars linking RDA outputs to the RDA's regional communities.

KPI WP2d Report and update on report

Description: Best practice guide

Target: 1 report at M12, and 1 update at month 36

Result: [Document available on Zenodo](#).

Comment: A guide specifically tailored for facilitators, co-chairs, and community managers working with RDA (Research Data Alliance) Working Groups (WGs). Drawing on lessons from the RDA TIGER project, it provides insight into how facilitation can accelerate WG effectiveness, help navigate RDA structures, and maximise impact.

A.1.2. Working Group KPIs

KPI 2.1 Social media sharing of WG ideas and call for membership - social media

Target: Weekly sharing of Group content across social media channels

WG Stage: C1 WG starting

Progress and Comments: Calls for membership for WGs starting were published via RDA social media channels, in particular in relation to kick-off webinars, at the request of WGs. Weekly posts for each WG were not feasible, as WG content developed in various paces.

Example posts:

- [Common Application Programming Interface \(API\) for machine-actionable Data Management Plans \(maDMPs\) Working Group](#)
- [GORC II kick-off meeting amplification / invite](#)
- [Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II \(MaLDReTH II\) Working Group kick off meeting amplification / invite](#)
- [RDA Reproducibility checklist WG in community review](#)

KPI 2.2 Sharing of WG ideas and call for membership - website posts

Target: Sharing of Group idea and call for membership on 3 partner websites (incl-RDA news items)

WG Stage: C1 WG Starting

Progress and Comments: This type of outreach took place 1) by posting calls for new members on the RDA website on dedicated WG pages, and 2) via direct communication with individuals/organisations identified during the landscape analysis, services, potential members identified either by the facilitators or the co-chairs and WG members.

Examples of website posts:

- [Kick-off of the Building Immune Digital Twins Working Group](#)

- [Join the Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities WG Kick-off Meeting](#)
- [Kick-off of the Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data Working Group](#)

KPI 2.3 Sharing of WG ideas and call for membership - events

Target: Presentation in at least 1 event (RDA or 3rd party)

WG Stage: C1 WG starting

Progress and Comments: WG outputs were promoted across third party events and conferences attended by the RDA TIGER consortium throughout the project (see also KPI 2.11 below).

Supported WG kick-off meetings were promoted as upcoming events on the RDA website. Example events:

- [New RDA working group on Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities \(SSH\) – kick off meeting](#)
- [New RDA Working Group on Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data – kick off meeting](#)
- [New RDA working group on FAIRification of genome sequence annotations \(tracks\) – Kickoff meetings in September](#)

KPI 2.4 Sharing of WG ideas and call for membership - newsletters

Target: At least 1 item/month included in the RDA Global newsletter

WG Stage: C1 WG starting

Progress and Comments:

2023

- [RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations Working Group\(DSTS_CS-WG\) - in Community Review in community review promotion in RDA Newsletter in July 2023](#)
- [RDA & ReSA: Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software \(PRO4RS\) WG Case Statement promotion in RDA Newsletter in September 2023](#)
- [RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG endorsement promotion in RDA Newsletter in October 2023](#)

2024

- [Harmonised Terminologies and Schemas for FAIR data in Materials Science and Related Domains Working Group Case Statement publication promotion in RDA Newsletter in January 2024](#)
- [Wind Energy Community Standards Working Group Case Statement for community review promotion in RDA Newsletter in February 2024](#)
- [FAIRification of Genomic Annotation New Working Group Case Statement in Community Review promotion in RDA Newsletter in March 2024](#)
- [Building Immune Digital Twins Community Review deadline reminder in RDA Newsletter in April 2024](#)
- [Community Review reminder for Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities and Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data new WGs in RDA](#)

[Newsletter in May 2024](#)

- [Reminder for Community Review for Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities in RDA Newsletter in June 2024](#)
- [\(TRSPs\) and FAIR Mappings WG in Community Review announcements in RDA Newsletter in July 2024](#)
- [Health data commons new WG in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in August 2024](#)

2025

- [GORC International Implementations \(GORC II WG\) and Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II \(MaLDReTH II\) Working Groups in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in January 2025](#)
- [Common Application Programming Interface \(API\) for machine-actionable Data Management Plans \(maDMPs\) Working Group in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in March 2025](#)
- [RDA Reproducibility Checklist Working Group in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in April 2025](#)
- [Common Application Programming Interface \(API\) for machine-actionable Data Management Plans \(maDMPs\) WG and Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II \(MaLDReTH II\) WG new WG features in RDA Newsletter in June 2025](#)

KPI 2.5 WG page unique views

Target: 30 unique page views during C1 stage.

WG Stage: (C1) WG starting

Progress and Comments: This KPI could not be meaningfully tracked across the project lifespan due to the RDA web platform migration and associated data gaps. In addition, many WGs in the C1 stage do not have a public web page while carrying out preparatory Statement of Work activities. Related service impact can be demonstrated through the increase in supported new RDA and WG members as reported in D6.5⁸⁹ (section 4.3, figure 8).

KPI 2.6 New WG members

Target: 20 (new) WG members by the end of the project

WG Stage: C1 WG starting

Progress and Comments: See D6.5 Annex 2

KPI 2.7 Unique group page views

Target: 30 per month

WG Stage: C2 (WG Work period)

Progress and Comments: See comment in KPI 2.5 above.

KPI 2.8 Creation of Group Collaterals

Target: at least 5 communication campaigns/packages during project lifetime

⁸⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877446>

WG Stage: C2 (WG Work period)
Progress and Comments:

- [‘Introducing the Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities Working Group’ video and promotional campaign](#)
- I-ADOPT Variable Modelling Workshops promotional campaign^{90 91 92}
- [Introducing the MOMSI Landscape Dashboard: A Tool for Mapping Multi-Omics Standards promotional campaign](#)
- [Repository Services - developing trust in the ecosystem \(TRSPs WG promotional campaign\)](#)
- [Shaping Responsible AI: Four New Recommendations from the AIDV Working Group](#)
- [Get Involved: RDA TIGER Calls to Action from the 24th RDA Plenary Meeting \(multiple WGs\)](#)

KPI 2.9 Group mention in RDA Global newsletter

Target: 1 per quarter

WG Stage: C2 (WG Work period)

Progress and Comments:

2023

- GORC IM WG co-located event promoted in RDA Newsletters in February 2023^{93 94}
- [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers \(TRSPs\) - Plenary session recap by WG Facilitator promoted at RDA Newsletter in November 2023](#)

2024

- [RDA Council Endorsement for the Wind Energy Community Standards Working Group announcement in RDA Newsletter in May 2024](#)
- [Endorsed Group announcement of FAIRification of Genomic Annotations Working Group in RDA Newsletter in June 2024](#)
- [Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG endorsement announcement in RDA Newsletter in July 2024](#)
- [Building Immune Digital Twins WG endorsement announcement in RDA Newsletter in August 2024](#)
- [Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities WG and Community-based Catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Services Providers \(TRSPs\) WG endorsement announcements in RDA Newsletter in September 2024](#)
- [Health Data Commons GORC Profile New Working Group announcement in RDA Newsletter in December 2024](#)
- [Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities Working Group](#)

⁹⁰ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7310627672135553024/>

⁹¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7304852371245858816/>

⁹² <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7298237496407085057>

⁹³ <https://archive.rd-alliance.org/rda-month-review-decade-data-plenary-20-tab-election-results-and-more>

⁹⁴ <https://archive.rd-alliance.org/rda-month-review-plenary-20-special-issue-and-other-news>

(SSH Vocab) feature in RDA newsletter in December 2024

2025

- [Secure Processing Environments for Open Science: Proposing Legal Foundations by the Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation WG output in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in February 2025](#)
- [FAIR Mappings Working Group feature in RDA Newsletter in February 2025](#)
- [GORC II WG feature in RDA Newsletter in March 2025](#)
- [Post-plenary WG session feature \(multiple WGs\), and The RDA Working Group on Ethics in Agricultural Data survey promotion in RDA Newsletter and website in April 2025](#)
- [Building Immune Digital Twins Working Group and HarmonisedMatChem Working Group external expert open calls in RDA Newsletter and website in April 2025](#)
- [KICK OFF MEETING: GORC International Implementations Working Group \(GORC II WG\) in RDA Newsletter and website in April 2025](#)
- [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\) & Research Software Alliance Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software \(PRO4RS\) Working Group 'other' output feature in RDA Newsletter in May 2025](#)
- [Introducing the MOMSI Landscape Dashboard: A Tool for Mapping Multi-Omics Standards feature in RDA Newsletter in May 2025](#)
- [MOMSI WG Multi-Omics Standard Landscape Review Curation Workflow & Interactive Web-based Dashboard Tool Supporting Output from Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration \(MOMSI\) Working Group in RDA Newsletter in June 2025](#)

KPI 2.10 Social Media Mentions

Target: Weekly sharing of Group content across social media channels

WG Stage: C2 (WG Work period)

Progress and Comments:

Example posts:

- RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG amplification^{95 96 97}
- [Plenary session promotion \(multiple WGs\)](#)
- [Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities WG meeting amplification](#)
- [RDA-CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services \(DSTS\) for Crisis Situations Working Group survey amplification](#)
- [Multi-omics Metadata Standards and Interoperability \(MOMSI\) Working Group](#)
- Ethics in Agricultural Data survey amplification^{98, 99}
- [BIDT activity promotion \(call for experts amplification for expert grant\)](#)

⁹⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7363827147972452353>

⁹⁶ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7349331630253060096>

⁹⁷ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7363827147972452353>

⁹⁸ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7328751450065375233>

⁹⁹ https://x.com/RDA_Europe/status/1917866861250650336?s=20

- [HarmonisedMatChem Working Group activity promotion \(call for experts amplification for expert grant\)](#)
- [Management and alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the SSH plenary session promotion](#)

KPI 2.11 Event presence

Target: Participation/promotion in at least 5 events per year (not inc. RDA Plenaries) in any capacity (poster, lightning talk, paper, etc).

WG Stage: C2 (WG Work period)

Progress and Comments:

Example WG promotion:

- [RDA TIGER lightning talk and poster at LIBER 2025 \(multiple WGs\)](#)
- [RDA TIGER poster and lightning talk at EGI 2025 \(multiple WGs\)](#)
- [RDA TIGER talk on the impact of RDA outputs to EOSC \(multiple WGs\)](#) and ‘Data for AI: From Readiness to Ethics’ panel discussion focused on the RDA AIDV WG at OSFair 2025.
- [IDCC2025 lightning talk \(multiple WGs\)](#) and [poster presentation \(multiple WGs\)](#)
- [Open Science Today and Tomorrow conference organized in Vilnius, Lithuania in October 2025 \(multiple WGs\)](#)

KPI 2.12 Group-Internal newsletter and/or bulletin

Target: 1 per month

WG Stage: C3 (WG end period)

Progress and Comments: Individual WG newsletters were not pursued, as the content relevant for each WG would be duplicated from the RDA Global Newsletter, and the new web platform allowed for efficient ad-hoc news posts also addressing time-critical announcements. Internal WG communications spotlighting specific items of interest were carried out by RDA TIGER for WGs across C1-C3 using mailing lists and the RDA web posting functionality often multiple times a month. Example internal communications process is presented in D6.5 Annex 3, figure 10¹⁰⁰.

KPI 2.13 Unique group page views

Target: 50 for the duration of the project

WG Stage: C3 (WG end period)

Progress and Comments: See comment in KPI 2.5 above; also, supported WGs at stage C3 span beyond the end of the RDA TIGER project.

KPI 2.14 Creation of Group collaterals

Target: at least 2 communication campaigns/packages during project lifetime

WG Stage: C3 (WG end period)

Progress and Comments:

- GORC International Model Communique drafting and production for two types of stakeholders, first created in 2023, updated in October 2025 ^{101 102}

¹⁰⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877446>

¹⁰¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14341230>

¹⁰² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14341560>

- National PID Strategies WG checklist visualisations and [infographic](#), and [white paper](#).

KPI 2.15 Group mention in RDA Global newsletter

Target: 1 per Output stage

WG Stage: C3 (WG end period)

Progress and Comments:

2023

- [National PID Strategies Working Group - Final Recommendations promoted in RDA Newsletter in September 2023](#)
- [GORC International Model Working Group - New Supporting Output In community review promoted in RDA Newsletters in September 2023](#)
- [GORC International Model Working Group output endorsements promoted in RDA Newsletter in October 2023](#)
- [GORC International Model Working Group output finalisation communication materials promoted in RDA Newsletter in November 2023](#)

2024

- [GORC International Model WG and Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG Recommendations in community review announcements in RDA Newsletter in July 2024](#)
- [Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG: AI Bill of Rights Recommendation, and Guidance for Ethics Committees Reviewing AI and DV recommendations in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in August 2024](#)
- [Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools recommendation in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in August 2024](#)
- [Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG: Shared Citation Library supporting output in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in August 2024](#)
- [RDA-OfR Mapping the Digital Landscape WG: Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools recommendation in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in September 2024](#)
- [The Global Open Research Commons International Model final output mention in RDA Newsletter in October 2024](#)
- [Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools final output mention in RDA Newsletter in November 2024](#)

2025

- [MOMSI WG Multi-Omics Standard Landscape Review Curation Workflow & Interactive Web-based Dashboard Tool supporting output in community review in RDA Newsletter in April 2025](#)
- [Four new recommendations from the Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) Working Group feature in RDA Newsletter in June 2025](#)
- [NEW BLOG — Shaping Responsible AI: Four New Recommendations from the AIDV Working Group By the Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG feature in RDA Newsletter in August 2025](#)

KPI 2.16 Social media mentions

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0 Project: 101094406.

Target: Weekly sharing of Group content across social media channels

WP Stage: C3 (WG end period)

Progress and Comments:

Example posts:

- [Cascade grant deliverable presentation for supported WG GORC IM WG](#)
- [Adoption story promotion for GORC IM WG](#)
- [Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG General WG promotion](#)
- Plenary session promotion (multiple WGs)^{103 104}
- [EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence & Data Visitation WG](#) activity promotion^{105 106}
- [RDA Reproducibility Checklist Working Group output community review amplification](#)

KPI 2.17 Event presence

Target: Participation/promotion in at least 2 events per year (not inc. RDA Plenaries) in any capacity (poster, lightning talk, paper, etc).

WG Stage: C3 (WG end period)

Progress and Comments:

Example events:

- [EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence & Data Visitation WG](#) Panel ‘Data for AI: From Readiness to Ethics’ at OSFair 2025. Panel composed of 2 WG co-chairs (Natalie Meyers, Elif Ecmekci), chaired by Alex Delipalta, Project Coordinator.^{107 108}
- [RDA TIGER poster at LIBER 2025 \(multiple WGs\)](#)
- RDA TIGER [poster](#) and [lightning talk](#) at EGI 2025 (multiple WGs)

KPI 2.18 Adoption outreach

Target: Target at least 2 adopters for each Recommendation via any means

WG Stage: C3 (WG end period)

Progress and Comments: All RDA TIGER WGs at finalisation stage provided a list of adopters, which have been contacted by WP2. At the time of writing, three adoption stories have been completed as part of

¹⁰³ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7384367297400053760>

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7383325138823393280>

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7348600501640290304>

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7338864695115718656>

¹⁰⁷ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7373982367184494592>

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.opensciencefair.eu/panels/data-for-ai-from-readiness-to-ethics>

this outreach for the GORC initiative^{109 110 111}, with multiple ongoing conversations with adopters towards the production of more adoption stories specifically for the AIDV and I-ADOPT WGs. All adoption stories produced with the support of RDA TIGER are listed on the [project web page](#).

109

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/adoption-stories/adopting-the-global-open-research-commons-gorc-model-reason/>

¹¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/adoption-stories/adopting-the-global-open-research-commons-gorc-model-surf/>

¹¹¹

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/adoption-stories/adopting-the-global-open-research-commons-model-the-case-of-eosc-data-commons/>

